

1 Numerical study of near-borehole coupled thermo-hydro-mechanical processes
2 during stimulation of a synthetic geothermal reservoir

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4 **Abstract**

5 Soft stimulation technologies have been proposed as a means to reduce the breakdown pressure and mitigate
6 the risk of induced seismicity during geothermal reservoir stimulation. Yet, the underlying mechanisms remain
7 poorly understood due to the complexity of the coupled thermo-hydro-mechanical (THM) processes. In this
8 work, a fully coupled THM model is developed to evaluate and compare the performance of different stimulation
9 scenarios (monotonic, stepwise injection rate, cyclic injection rate or temperature, and stepwise combined with
10 cyclic injection rate stimulation) on a synthetic, highly permeable reservoir with near-borehole clogging. Sim-
11 ulation results show that stepwise injection rate stimulation yields the most favourable outcomes, followed by
12 the stepwise injection rate combined with cyclic injection rate stimulation. On the other hand, fatigue effects
13 are seen to play a negligible role in the improved performance since the tensile stress at the fracture tip is
14 relaxed with the continuous fracture growth. In addition, cyclic injection temperature stimulation is generally
15 neither better nor worse than monotonic stimulation, but has slightly different characteristics, creating more
16 local damage controlled by the period of the injection cycle. Cyclic injection rate stimulation can slightly re-
17 duce the peak pressure, compared with monotonic stimulation, but only when the injection rate is low. The
18 reduction in peak pressure occurs due to the combination of thermally-induced stresses associated with cooling
19 and incremental damage rather than any influence of fatigue. Stepwise or low-frequency cyclic injection rate
20 stimulation are suggested rather than a high-frequency cyclic injection rate stimulation, while injection with
21 cyclic temperatures is suggested when more local damage is wanted.

22 *Keywords:* Geothermal energy, Soft stimulation, Thermo-hydro-mechanics, Fatigue damage

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23 1. Introduction

24 Stimulation technologies are commonly performed operations to improve well performance in geo-energy reser-
25 voirs. However, conventional hydraulic stimulation has caused environmental concerns, especially the risk of
26 induced seismicity. For example, the hydraulic stimulations performed in the Enhanced Geothermal System
27 (EGS) project in Basel (Switzerland), in Strasbourg (France) and in Pohang (South Korea) were reported to
28 induce felt earthquakes with magnitude of 3.4, 3.6 and 5.4 respectively, leading to the termination of the projects
29 [1, 2, 3]. Alternatively, soft stimulation technology has been proposed to reduce the risk of induced seismicity
30 while achieving the desired stimulation performance, since it requires lower pumping pressure. Several soft
31 stimulation methods, including cyclic injection rate [4] and thermal stimulation [5], have been demonstrated
32 to be effective, with different underlying mechanisms. Cyclic hydraulic stimulation requires alternating phases
33 of high and low flow rates to induce fatigue damage. Its ability to lower the breakdown pressure has been
34 demonstrated in laboratory experiments [6], mine-scale experiments [7] and field tests [4]. Thermal stimulation
35 requires the injection of cold water to induce rock contraction, therefore thermally-induced stress, which could
36 re-activate pre-existing fractures, and create new fractures at lower pumping pressure [8, 5]. Successful thermal
37 stimulation demonstrations include the test on Well H40 & H41 at the Los Humeros field in Mexico [5] and the
38 test on HE-8 at Hellisheidi in Iceland [8].

39 Although successful implementations of cyclic and thermal stimulations have been reported, the underlying
40 mechanisms remain poorly understood due to the complexity of the coupled thermo-hydro-mechanical (THM)
41 processes including cyclic effects, illustrated in Fig. 1. During stimulation with cold water, the cooling effect
42 can induce volumetric strain (shrinkage) in the rock mass which is restrained by surrounding media, leading
43 to (tensile) thermal stresses. This thermal-to-mechanical effect, can induce new fractures or re-activate natural
44 fractures. Conversely, the mechanical deformation may result in energy loss, leading to changes in temperature.
45 However, this mechanical-to-thermal effect is usually small and thus can be ignored in geo-mechanical analyses
46 [9, 10]. In addition, fluid properties such as viscosity and density [11] are influenced by temperature, and
47 temperature changes may therefore induce or alter fluid flow. This thermal-to-hydraulic effect inevitably leads
48 to injectivity decline during cold water injection. In contrast, any change in fluid pressure distribution induces
49 a flow, which will influence heat transfer, thus the temperature field. This hydraulic-to-thermal effect largely
50 controls the efficiency of heat extraction from the subsurface. Moreover, for the hydraulic-to-mechanical effect,
51 rock deformation depends on the effective stress, which combines the total stress and pore pressure according to
52 the effective stress principle [12]. On the other hand, deformation of the rock mass or the creation of new fluid
53 pathways (i.e. new fractures or re-activated natural fractures) can change the fluid flow pattern. In addition,
54 cyclic injection of stimulation fluid can reduce fluid and heat fluxes, compared to continuous injection, and cause
55 cyclic pressure build-up and warming up, therefore resulting in cyclic changes in the stress field. Cyclic stress
56 changes may lead to fatigue damage, or control fracture propagation, thus can largely influence the stimulation
57 performance. For instance, a field test performed on well PX-1 at the Pohang EGS project site demonstrated
58 that cyclic stimulation was able to improve injectivity from 0.5 L/(s·MPa) to 2.6 L/(s·MPa) while managing the
59 seismic activity to remain below the target threshold of M_w 2.0 [4, 13]. However, whether fatigue effect plays a
60 dominant role in the injectivity or not, is yet clear. A thorough understanding of the coupled THM processes
61 under cyclic stimulation is therefore of significant importance to understand the underlying mechanisms and to
62 optimise the stimulation protocol.

Fig. 1: Description of the interactions between thermo-hydro-mechanical (THM) processes.

63 Numerical simulation provides a possible way to investigate the underlying mechanisms and compare the stimu-
64 lation performances under various stimulation strategies. Yoshioka et al. [14] used the GeoMechanical Reservoir
65 Simulator to investigate the optimal design of water stimulation to a synthetic 3D reservoir, in which the fluid
66 flow was allowed to happen in a single fracture plane. Yet, the model remained simple as the borehole was sim-
67 plified as a line source and the matrix was assumed to be impermeable. In addition, the investigated stimulation
68 scenarios were limited to continuous (followed by shut-in) and stepwise stimulation. Yoon et al. [15] used the
69 Particle Flow Code^{2D} to study the optimised hydraulic stimulation of intact and naturally fractured reservoir.
70 The investigated scenarios involved continuous and cyclic styles of pressure-controlled and flow rate-controlled
71 injections. However, the cyclic frequency was low (cyclic period around 3 hours) and the injection well was
72 simplified as a point, thus ignoring the near-borehole effects. Jacquy et al. [16] constructed a 3D model with
73 the hydraulic fracture being represented as boundary condition to simulate the cyclic hydraulic stimulation ex-
74 ercises performed in the well Gt GrSk 4/05 in Groß Schönebeck. Though the fracture opening was considered,
75 this model was not able to simulate the fracture initiation and propagation and thermal effects are not included.
76 Cheng et al. [17] generated a 3D stochastic fracture network model to simulate the the phase 2.2 stimulation
77 at the Newberry EGS site, with the fully THM processes considered. Yoo et al. [18] used TOUGH-FLAC
78 simulator to simulate the hydraulic stimulation treatment to PX-1 and PX-2 in Pohang field, yet not included
79 the thermal effect and focused on the pre-existing fractures. Wang et al. [19] constructed 3D THM model of
80 fractured reservoir to simulate the hydro-shearing stimulation at the Utah FORGE site, but the borehole was
81 also simplified and considered stimulation scenarios were limited. There are other works that included the real
82 borehole to study the near-borehole fracture initiation and propagation, such as Zhang et al. [20], Xi et al.
83 [21] and Wei et al. [22]. However, their models were limited to very small scales (cm). In brief, a model that
84 can simultaneously consider coupled THM processes, fatigue damage, and the initiation and propagation of
85 fractures on a realistic scale is rarely reported. The major challenges include modelling both conductive and
86 convective heat transfer in the rock matrix and the growing fractures, which can cause numerical instability due
87 to high Peclet number and introduce artificial compliance. In addition, the simulation of the fracture initiation
88 and propagation under fully THM coupling can largely increase the computational burden. Therefore, a smart
89 and flexible inclusion of the fracture growth is necessary.

90 This study aims to gain new insights into the mechanisms and effectiveness of various stimulation strategies

91 (monotonic, stepwise, cyclic and stepwise combined with cyclic stimulation) in the presence of near-borehole
92 clogging. In the following, the numerical method is briefed, followed by an introduction to the synthetic reservoir
93 and the investigated scenarios. Results and discussions are then presented, followed by a conclusion.

94 **2. Numerical method**

95 *2.1. Modelling approach*

96 Modelling fracture behaviour in continuous porous media (e.g., rock) is a non-trivial task, as discontinuities
97 break displacement compatibility of standard FEM formulations and pose strong singularities in the solutions.
98 To mitigate these difficulties, zero-thickness interface elements, a conceptually simple technique, are used to
99 represent the discontinuities in this work. Interface elements are inserted in between continuum elements to
100 represent pre-existing or potential fractures, as shown in Fig. 2. A 2D modelling approach is used, with each
101 interface element having in total 9 nodes, equally distributed on top, mid, and bottom planes (Fig. 2b). For an
102 unloaded interface element, these three planes coincide in the same position.

103 The bottom and top faces of the interface element share nodes with the continuum element, with each shared
104 node possessing four degrees of freedom, namely x and y coordinates, water pressure p_w , and temperature
105 T . In contrast, the mid-plane nodes include only two degrees of freedom, namely the water pressure p_w and
106 temperature T . In this way, different constitutive laws can be used for the continuum and the discontinuities,
107 allowing for a more realistic representation of the heat and fluid fluxes along and across the fracture. The
108 nodes of the bottom and top faces of the interface which are in contact with each other are pre-determined to
109 both improve robustness and decrease computation. This, however, reduces the amount of shear displacement
110 possible.

111 In this work, the thermal processes is included in the interface element, under the assumptions that the material
112 is always water saturated (i.e., without considering a gas phase). Additionally, the water viscosity is dependent
113 on temperature while water density is dependent on both water pressure and temperature. In the following sec-
114 tion, the mathematical formulations for both the continuum and discontinuities are described. The formulations
115 are implemented in the FEM code LAGAMINE [23], in which the formulation of continuum was implemented
116 by Collin et al. [24] and the formulation of the interface element was implemented by Liaudat et al. [25] and
117 Luo et al. [26]. The extensive verifications and validations of the proposed methods can be found in Luo et al.
118 [26] and in Luo et al. [27], and are not repeated here.

(a) Insertion of interface elements in between continuum elements (light blue).

(b) Interface element

Fig. 2: Finite elements used. (a) Interface elements in between continuum elements to represent pre-existing or potential cracking paths, and (b) Element node numbering, nodal degrees of freedom and local basis

119 2.2. Governing equations for the continuum porous medium

120 The governing equations follow the formulation proposed by Collin et al. [24] Here the equations with corresponding constitutive laws are briefly introduced.

122 2.2.1. Hydraulic problem

123 The water mass balance equation without any internal source or sink reads:

$$\frac{\partial(\phi\rho_w)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_w \mathbf{v}_w) = 0 \quad (1)$$

124 where ϕ is the porosity, ρ_w [kg/m³] is the water density, and \mathbf{v}_w [m/s] is the Darcy velocity vector. The latter is defined as:

$$\mathbf{v}_w = -\frac{\mathbf{K}}{\mu_w} \nabla p_w \quad (2)$$

126 where \mathbf{K} [m²] is the intrinsic permeability tensor and μ_w [Pa · s] is the water dynamic viscosity.

127 Assuming isotropy, the intrinsic permeability tensor is defined as $\mathbf{K} = K\mathbf{I}$, where K is the scalar permeability and \mathbf{I} is the identity tensor. Permeability is assumed to be a function of porosity according to:

$$K = K_0 \frac{(1 - \phi_0)^m}{\phi_0^n} \frac{\phi^n}{(1 - \phi)^m} \quad (3)$$

129 where K_0 [m²] is the permeability for $\phi = \phi_0$. n is assumed to be 3 and m to be 2 [28].

130 In the above-mentioned equations, the properties of water are a function of temperature and water pressure.

131 Accordingly, the water density and dynamic viscosity [29] are calculated as:

$$\rho_w = \rho_{w0} \left[1 + \frac{p_w - p_{w0}}{\kappa_w} - \beta_w (T - T_0) \right] \quad (4)$$

132 and

$$\mu_w = 0.6612(T - 229)^{-1.562} \quad (5)$$

133 where ρ_{w0} [kg/m³] is the water density defined at the reference pressure p_{w0} [Pa] and temperature T_0 [K], κ_w [1/Pa], the water compressibility, and β_w [1/K], the thermal expansion coefficient.

135 *2.2.2. Mechanical problem*

136 If equilibrium state is assumed and if gravity is neglected, the equation of momentum conservation reads:

$$\nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{0} \quad (6)$$

137 where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ [Pa] is Cauchy's total stress tensor.

138 The considered mechanical constitutive law for the bulk rock is the classical law [30]. If compressive stress and
139 strain are defined as negative, the thermo-poro-elastic constitutive law reads:

$$\Delta \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbb{C} : \Delta \boldsymbol{\epsilon} - \Delta p_w \mathbf{I} - \beta_b K_b \Delta T \mathbf{I} \quad (7)$$

140 where \mathbb{C} is the 4th-order elastic stiffness tensor, $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ is the strain tensor, α is the Biot coefficient, \mathbf{I} is the 2nd-order
141 identity tensor, β_b [1/K] is the bulk volumetric thermal expansion coefficient, and K_b [Pa] is the drained bulk
142 modulus.

143 *2.2.3. Thermal problem*

144 Under the assumption of local thermal equilibrium, with no internal source or sink, the equation of energy
145 conservation reads:

$$\frac{\partial[(\rho c_p)_b T]}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q}_T = 0 \quad (8)$$

146 where, $(\rho c_p)_b = (1 - \phi)(\rho c_p)_s + \phi(\rho c_p)_w$ is the bulk volumetric heat capacity (with c_p [J/(kg · K)] being the
147 phase specific heat capacity, ρ the phase density, and the subscripts s and w referring to the solid and the water
148 phases, respectively), and \mathbf{q}_T [J/(m² · s)] is the heat flux vector. The latter is given by:

$$\mathbf{q}_T = -\lambda_b \nabla T + \rho_w c_{pw} \mathbf{v}_w (T - T_0) \quad (9)$$

149 where the first term corresponds to Fourier's law with the bulk thermal conductivity given by λ_b [J/(m · s · K)]
150 = $(1 - \phi)\lambda_s + \phi\lambda_w$, and the second term corresponds to the heat advection due to water flow.

151 *2.3. Governing equations for the discontinuities*

152 The mechanical and hydraulic governing equations for the interface elements are inherited from Liaudat et al.
153 [25] with the gas phase being neglected. Additionally, the governing equations for thermal processes are included
154 here. Note that the following equations are tailored for 2D problems.

155 *2.3.1. Hydraulic problem*

156 The mass balance for water in a differential volume of discontinuity *wdl* reads:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(w \rho_w) + \frac{\partial q_w^l}{\partial l} - q_w^b - q_w^t = 0 \quad (10)$$

157 where w [m] is the width of the discontinuity, q_w^l [kg/(m · s)] is the longitudinal water mass flow, and q_w^b and
158 q_w^t [kg/(m² · s)] are the transversal water mass fluxes incoming to the discontinuity from surrounding continuum
159 medium [25].

160 The mass fluxes in Eq. (10) can be expanded as:

$$q_w^l = \rho_w v_w^l; \quad q_w^b = \rho_w v_w^b; \quad q_w^t = \rho_w v_w^t \quad (11)$$

161 where v_w^l [m²/s], v_w^b [m/s] and v_w^t [m/s] are the longitudinal and transversal (top and bottom) volumetric fluxes.
162 These fluxes obtained from the following generalised Darcy's law:

$$v_w^l = -\frac{t^l}{\mu_w} \frac{\partial p_w^m}{\partial l}; \quad v_w^b = -\frac{k^b}{\mu_w} \dot{p}_w^b; \quad v_w^t = -\frac{k^t}{\mu_w} \dot{p}_w^t \quad (12)$$

163 where t^l [m³] is the longitudinal hydraulic coefficient, k^b [m²] and k^t [m²] are the transversal permeability of the
 164 interface, p_w^m [Pa] is the water pressure at the middle plane, and \dot{p}_w^b [Pa] and \dot{p}_w^t [Pa] are the transversal pressure
 165 jumps between the bottom and top face and the mid-plane, respectively. The transversal pressure drops are
 166 defined as:

$$\dot{p}_w^b = (p_w^m - p_w^b); \quad \dot{p}_w^t = (p_w^m - p_w^t) \quad (13)$$

167 where p_w^b and p_w^t are the water pressures at the bottom and top sides of the discontinuity.

168 The longitudinal hydraulic coefficient t^l is estimated using the Reynolds lubrication equation, which describes
 169 the laminar flow of an incompressible and Newtonian fluid flowing between two parallel plates [31]. It reads:

$$t^l = \frac{r_n^3}{12} + t_0^l \quad (14)$$

170 where r_n [m] is the normal separation of the interface, and t_0^l [m³] is the initial longitudinal hydraulic coefficient,
 171 which makes it possible to assign an initial longitudinal transmissivity to the discontinuity even if it is closed
 172 from the mechanical point of view. The longitudinal hydraulic coefficient t^l , defined in Eq. (11), plays the same
 173 role in the hydraulic governing equations of the discontinuity as the intrinsic permeability \mathbf{K} in the hydraulic
 174 governing equations of the continuum. Both parameters account only for the geometrical characteristics of the
 175 medium through which the liquid fluxes, i.e., they are independent of the fluid properties. The fluid properties
 176 (as well as the time dimension) are introduced via the water dynamic viscosity μ_w in Eqs. (2) and (9), for the
 177 continuum and discontinuities, respectively.

178 The width w will evolve with the normal separation of interface r_n :

$$w = r_n + w_0 \quad (15)$$

179 where w_0 [m] can be set to be non-zero to assign an initial storage volume to the discontinuity even if it is
 180 mechanically closed [25].

181 2.3.2. Mechanical problem

182 The equation of momentum conservation for the interface element reads as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}_c}{\partial l} = \mathbf{0} \quad (16)$$

183 where l is the longitudinal axis of the interface element, and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_c = [\sigma_n, \sigma_l]$ [Pa] is the total stress on the interface
 184 mid-plane, with σ_n and σ_l being the normal and shear stress components on that plane. In this paper, mode I
 185 fracturing is considered. The shear stress component is therefore not discussed here.

186 For the mechanical constitutive behaviour of the discontinuity, the bilinear traction-separation law schematically
 187 depicted in Fig. 3 is used [32, 25]. More advanced constitutive laws can be incorporated easily into the code.
 188 This bilinear law can describe fracture behaviours characterised by six parameters: the maximum tension or
 189 shear strength σ_{n0} [Pa] or σ_{l0} [Pa], the normal or shear "cracking" separation r_{n0} [m] or r_{l0} [m], and the normal
 190 or shear debonding separation r_{nc} [m] or r_{lc} . Conventionally, the stress paths are represented by the black
 191 lines with the un-loading path represented by the black dashed lines in tensile and shear branches depicted
 192 respectively in Fig. 3a and 3b. The tensile branch is modified to take into account the fatigue damage. After

193 m cycles, the stress path is represented by the blue line in Fig. 3a, showing that the tensile strength is reduced
 194 from σ_{n0} to σ_{nm} . When the cycle number reaches the fatigue life (the number of cycles a material can withstand
 195 before failure under a given loading amplitude) of the material, M_f , the tensile strength is further reduced to
 196 σ_{nMf} . Any loading below the threshold strength σ_{nMf} will not induce damages to the material no matter how
 197 many cycles are implemented.

Fig. 3: The elasto-damage law. (a) Tensile branch incorporating the fatigue damage; (b) Shear branch

198 In the loading condition, the normal and tangential (to the mid-plane of the interface element) stresses are given
 199 by the following expressions:

$$\sigma'_n = \begin{cases} (1 - D)K_{nm}r_n & \text{if } r_n \geq 0 \\ K_{n0}r_n & \text{if } r_n \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

$$\sigma_1 = (1 - D)K_{10}r_1 \quad (18)$$

200 where σ'_n [Pa] represents Terzaghi's effective normal stress, defined as $\sigma'_n = \sigma_n + p_w^m$, and $K_{n0} = \sigma_{n0}/r_{n0}$ [Pa/m]
 201 is the initial normal slope. $K_{nm} = \sigma_{nm}/r_{n0}$ is the normal stiffness after m th cycles and $\sigma_{nm} = (1 - D_f)\sigma_{n0}$.
 202 D_f is the fatigue damage variable and will be defined later. σ_1 and r_1 are the tangential stress and separation
 203 respectively, and $K_{10} = \sigma_{10}/r_{10}$ is the tangential slope. When an interface element is used to represent natural
 204 fractures, the normal slope can have a physical meaning, interpreted as fracture stiffness, for instance, as a result
 205 of interpenetration of fracture surfaces due to presence of asperities [33, 34]. In the context of this paper, K_{n0}
 206 is interpreted as penalty coefficients, thus allowing negligible interpenetration of fracture surfaces regardless of
 207 their roughness [33]. To enforce the contact constraints, the slope should be set high enough to reduce artificial
 208 compliance [25]. However, the choice of their values is a trade-off between having artificial compliance and
 209 having numerical convergence problems. Additionally, D is the damage variable ranging from 0 (intact rock) to
 210 1 (fully separated fracture). This damage variable evolves as follows:

$$D = \min\left(\frac{\bar{\omega}}{1 + \bar{\omega}\eta}, 1\right) \quad (19)$$

$$\bar{\omega} = \max(\omega) \quad (20)$$

$$\omega = \left\langle \left(\frac{\langle r_n \rangle}{r_{n0}}\right)^\beta + \left(\frac{|r_1|}{r_{10}}\right)^{1/\beta} - 1 \right\rangle \quad (21)$$

$$\eta = 1 - \frac{r_{n0}}{r_{nc}} = 1 - \frac{r_{10}}{r_{1c}} \quad (22)$$

where ω is a positive scalar that defines the mechanical degradation of the interface element for a given normal separations, $\bar{\omega}$ is a history variable that stores the maximum value reached by ω during the loading history, and $\langle \cdot \rangle = (\cdot + |\cdot|)/2$ is the Macaulay bracket. β is a material parameter that characterise the mixed mode damage and is assumed to be 1 in this work [25]. The above equations state that if the separation r_n is less than the normal crack separation r_{n0} , the damage variable D is then zero. If $r_{n0} < r_n < r_{nc}$, D is between 0 and 1, determined by the ratio of $(r_n - r_{n0})/(r_{nc} - r_{n0})$. Otherwise if r_n is beyond the debonding separation r_{nc} , D is forced to be 1, indicating a completely separation of the interface element.

To determine the fatigue damage variable, a linear strength degradation is assumed [21, 35]. Thus, when subjected to constant-amplitude cyclic loading (Fig. 4a), it is defined as:

$$D_f = \left(1 - \frac{\sigma'_A}{\sigma_{n0}}\right) \frac{m}{M_f} \quad (23)$$

where σ'_A [Pa] is the amplitude of the cyclic loading (effective stress). M_f is the fatigue life (maximum number of cycles until failure) under a specific constant-amplitude cyclic loading.

When subjected to varying-amplitude cyclic loading shown in (Fig. 4b), Equation 23 can be further developed based on the Palmgren-Miner's rule, which reads:

$$D_f = \sum_i \left(1 - \frac{\sigma'_{Ai}}{\sigma_{n0}}\right) \frac{1}{M_{fi}} \quad (24)$$

where i indicates the i th cyclic loading that has a maximum amplitude of σ'_{Ai} , as shown in Fig. 4b. M_{fi} is the fatigue life corresponding to the applied loading level σ'_{Ai} .

An empirical S-N relationship is used as a criterion to determine the fatigue life M_{fi} , which relates the maximum value of the cyclic loading (σ'_{Ai}) to the fatigue life M_{fi} of the rock. This relationship has been widely used in metals, concrete, and rocks [35, 36, 37, 21]. It reads [37, 21]:

$$\frac{\sigma'_{Ai}}{\sigma_{n0}} = a \log_{10} M_{fi} + b \quad (25)$$

where a and b are model parameters that can be determined from experimental data.

Fig. 4: Different loading scenarios.

230 Moreover, mechanical viscosity is added to the contact stress to resolve the solution jump that can result in
 231 numerical divergence [38, 25] :

$$\sigma'_n = \sigma_n + p_w^m + \sigma_v \quad \text{with} \quad \sigma_v = \zeta \frac{\partial r_n}{\partial t} \quad (26)$$

232 where ζ [Pa · s/m] is the viscosity added to resolve large fast changes in the solution, which occur faster than
 233 the time discretisation, and can cause numerical divergence. The added viscosity ζ slows down the strain rate
 234 and thus stabilised the solution. Detailed discussion on the solution jumps and how the added viscosity helps
 235 mitigate this issue can be found in other works [38, 25].

236 2.3.3. Thermal problem

237 The conservation of energy, in terms of temperature, applied to a differential volume of discontinuity *wdl* reads:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(w\rho_w c_{pw} T^m) + \frac{\partial q_T^l}{\partial l} - q_T^b - q_T^t = 0 \quad (27)$$

238 where q_T^s [J/(m² · s)] is the rate of change of the heat stored in the discontinuity, q_T^l [J/(m · s)] is the longitudinal
 239 heat flux, q_T^b [J/(m² · s)] and q_T^t [J/(m² · s)] are the normal heat fluxes incoming from the surrounding continuum
 240 medium via bottom and top faces to the discontinuity, respectively.

241 The terms in Eq. (27) can be expanded as:

$$q_T^l = -w\lambda_w \frac{\partial T^m}{\partial l} + c_{pw} q_w^l T^m \quad (28)$$

$$q_T^b = -\lambda_w \frac{2\check{T}^b}{\max(w, \bar{w})} + c_{pw} q_w^b \check{T}^b \quad (29)$$

$$q_T^t = -\lambda_w \frac{2\check{T}^t}{\max(w, \bar{w})} + c_{pw} q_w^t \check{T}^t \quad (30)$$

242 where $\check{T}^b = T^m - T^b$ and $\check{T}^t = T^m - T^t$ are the temperature jumps between the bottom or top face and the
 243 mid-plane, with T^m , T^b and T^t being the temperatures at the mid-plane, bottom and top face of interface
 244 element, respectively, and λ_w is the thermal conductivity of the water. \bar{w} is a penalty coefficient to avoid
 245 singularity when interface elements are used to provide potential cracking paths in intact rock. The penalty
 246 coefficient should be as small as possible to reduce the artificial compliance.

247 3. Synthetic reservoir with clogged near-borehole area

248 The potential of stimulation is analysed on a synthetic case of a sandstone reservoir with clogged near-borehole
 249 zone. The synthetic reservoir is assumed to be a non-fractured sandstone reservoir, inspired by the Delft
 250 Sandstone Formation. A borehole with a radius of 0.2 m is located at the centre of a circular domain with
 251 a radius of 500 m (to ensure no boundary effects) and a thickness of 100 m. A near-borehole zone with a
 252 radius of 5 m is assumed to be clogged, with impaired permeability decreasing to 1% of the initial reservoir
 253 permeability K_0 . Clogging with a (much) smaller distance from the borehole wall could exist, but in this case,
 254 either chemical or mechanical means could probably be used to rehabilitate the well. Therefore, a reasonably
 255 extreme case has been selected. Anisotropic clogging pattern is likely existing due to actual drilling intrusion
 256 and mineral dissolution/precipitation. Yet isotropic clogging is assumed in this work for simplicity.

257 Representative reservoir data is collected from the TU Delft campus geothermal project. Comprehensive data
258 has been collected during the drilling of the doublet [39], including from cores and a large suite of open-hole well
259 logs in the reservoir section of both wells. With regional knowledge, the data from the doublet and surrounding
260 wells, a normal faulting regime can be assumed. Logging data and regional knowledge allows an estimation of
261 the pore pressure to be around 21 MPa and in-situ stresses to be $\sigma_v = 48$ MPa, $\sigma_H = 42$ MPa and $\sigma_h = 38$
262 MPa, at depth of 2000 m. According to regional studies, the azimuth of the σ_H is between N130°E and N150°E.
263 After drilling, the well DEL-GT-01 has been tested by means of a gas-lift, providing valuable information of
264 the reservoir quality, such as permeability and temperature. In addition, previous oil and gas explorations and
265 other nearby geothermal projects provide a large dataset including hydraulic, thermal and mechanical properties
266 [40, 41]. The properties used in exploratory analysis are summarised in Tab. 1.

Table 1: Reservoir data for the exploratory analyses, based on the Delft Sandstone Formation [40, 41, 39, 42]

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Reservoir thickness	H_r	100	m
Total vertical stress	σ_v	48	MPa
Total maximum horizontal stress	σ_H	42	MPa
Total minimum horizontal stress	σ_h	38	MPa
Initial reservoir pressure	p_{wi}	21	MPa
Initial reservoir temperature	T_i	353	K
Reservoir porosity	ϕ	0.17	-
Solid density	ρ_s	2650	kg/m ³
Reservoir permeability	K	1.6×10^{-12}	m ²
Impaired permeability	K'	1.6×10^{-14}	m ²
Young's modulus	E	11.5	GPa
Poisson's ratio	ν	0.15	-
Unconfined compressive strength	σ_c	48	MPa
Tensile strength*	σ_t	4.8	MPa
Internal friction coefficient	μ	0.75	-
Volumetric thermal expansion coefficient	β	6.5×10^5	1/K
Thermal conductivity	λ	3	W/(m·K)
Specific heat capacity	c_{ps}	924.5	J/(kg·K)

*: σ_t is assumed to be 1/10 of σ_c , which is derived from logging data.

267 4. Numerical model

268 4.1. Geometry and mesh

269 To simulate the near-borehole coupled processes under thermo-hydraulic stimulation in the synthetic reservoir,
270 a symmetric plane strain 2D horizontal model with a domain radius of 500 m is constructed, shown in Fig. 5a.
271 The domain is composed of 3 material groups with radius from (0.2 m - 5 m), (5 m - 10 m) and (10 m - 500
272 m) respectively, in order to assign different properties to the clogged zone (0.2 m - 5 m) and unclogged zone (5
273 m -500 m), and to insert interface elements only in the near-borehole domain (0.2 m - 10 m). A borehole with
274 radius of 0.2 m is placed at the centre.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5: Schematic of the (a) Numerical model domain with boundary conditions. Not to scale. An environment node is used to mimic the wellbore, on which the injection rate is applied. The environment node is connected with the borehole nodes without flow resistance. Interface (IF) elements are inserted in between all the continuum elements within the inner region from 0.2 m - 10 m radius (the dark gray region). Outside this region, only continuum elements are used; and (b) meshing of the domain.

275 The model is meshed with 2nd-order triangular continuum elements, with interface elements inserted in between
 276 all the continuum elements within the inner region from 0.2 m - 10 m radius to enable arbitrary fracture initiation
 277 and propagation near the borehole (see Fig. 5b). This approach ensures reasonable reservoir performance taking

278 into account the far-field behaviour while minimising computational and memory demands by avoiding interface
279 elements throughout the entire domain. As shown in [26], insertion of interface elements in between continuum
280 elements to provide potential cracking paths in intact rock will introduce artificial compliance that have an
281 impact on thermo-hydro-mechanical response. To reduce the mechanical artificial compliance, the stiffness of
282 the interface elements is set as high as possible without causing numerical difficulties, i.e. a lack of convergence,
283 as discussed in [26]. The hydraulic and thermal artificial compliances can be reduced in a similar way, by
284 assigning a high transversal transmissivity of the interface element to reduce the flow resistance. The detail of
285 reducing the hydraulic and thermal artificial compliances is presented in [Appendix A](#).

286 *4.2. Initial and boundary conditions.*

287 The initial stresses are $\sigma_h = 38$ MPa in x direction and $\sigma_H = 42$ MPa in y direction. The displacements normal
288 to the symmetry axis (bottom as shown in [Fig. 5a](#)) are fixed in the y direction, while the displacement is
289 fixed in both x and y directions along the far-field boundary. A uniform normal load, which is equal to the
290 steady-state injection pressure, is distributed around the borehole throughout the simulation time, leading to a
291 zero effective stress around the borehole. In addition to the mechanical boundary conditions, temperature and
292 fluid pressure are fixed to their initial values at the far-field boundary. A monotonic q_{2D} (kg/(m·s)), leading
293 to a total injection rate Q_{inj} ($m^3/h, = 2 \times 3600 \times H_r \times \rho_w \times q_{2D}$) for the open-hole section with thickness of
294 H , is applied on an environment node, which is connected to the borehole nodes without resistance to mimic
295 the well-bore. The temperature at the borehole wall is fixed at the injection temperature T_{inj} . Note that the
296 heat exchange between the wellbore fluid, casing and the formation is not included in this model, and could
297 overestimate the thermally-induced stresses.

298 *4.3. Input parameters.*

299 A linear elastic model is used for the continuum elements, while the previously developed elasto-damage law
300 that incorporates the fatigue damage into the tensile branch is used for the interface elements. The parameters
301 assigned to the continuum elements are presented in [Tab. 1](#), while the parameters for the interface elements
302 are summarised below in the [Tab. 2](#). Note that the initial longitudinal transmissivity of the interface element
303 is determined as equivalence to the impaired permeability of the continuum element [26], while the transversal
304 transmissivity is set high to reduce the artificial compliance.

305 The parameters a and b that describe the S-N relationship are determined by fitting the experimental data
306 collected from literature. All the strength used was measured using sandstone rock samples. The fitting curve
307 is shown in [Fig. 6](#).

Fig. 6: S-N relationship determined by fitting the experimental data collected from the literature.

Table 2: Input parameters for the interface elements used in the model

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Tensile strength	σ_{n0}	4.8	MPa
Tensile cracking separation	r_{n0}	10^{-7}	m
Tensile debonding separation	r_{nc}	10^{-6}	m
Shear strength	σ_{l0}	32	MPa
Shear cracking separation	r_{l0}	10^{-7}	m
Shear debonding separation	r_{lc}	10^{-6}	m
Mechanical viscosity	ζ	10^{14}	Pa·s/m
Parameter a	a	-0.0361	-
Parameter b	b	0.9926	-
Initial aperture	w_0	10^{-5}	m
Initial longitudinal transmissivity (non-clogged)	t_0^l	1.6×10^{-17}	m^3
Initial longitudinal transmissivity (clogged)	t_0^l	1.6×10^{-19}	m^3
Initial transversal transmissivity (in both cases)	$t_0^{b/t}$	10^{-10}	m^3
Stabilisation coefficient	$\delta \cdot h$	10	m

*: δ is the tuning parameter and h is the element length.

They are used in both longitudinal and transversal heat transfer in the interface elements to stabilise the numerical solution.

308 5. Investigated scenarios

309 The model including interface elements (with stabilisation and interface element parameters selected for accu-
 310 racy) will be used to study various synthetic stimulation scenarios with fully coupled THM processes and fatigue
 311 damage considered, allowing fracture initiation and propagation. Different stimulations, including monotonic,
 312 stepwise injection rate, cyclic injection rate or temperature stimulation and stepwise combined with cyclic rate
 313 stimulation scenarios will be simulated based on the reservoir with clogged near-borehole zone (assuming a
 314 clogged radius of 5 m where the permeability is reduced to $0.01 K_0$) to evaluate the stimulation performance of
 315 different stimulation strategies. Considering the large computational burden and the soft stimulation practice
 316 performed in Pohang geothermal field [4], the total operation period is restricted in 5 days. Tab. 3 summarises
 317 the investigated scenarios, which are further detailed below.

Table 3: Synthetic injection scenarios. The total injection time is 120 h. In each cycle of the scenario $C1$, the ΔT is kept at 40 K for Δt , which can be 5 hours or 10 hours, and then kept at 0 K for another $0.9 \Delta t$. In each cycle of scenario $C2$ and $C3$, the Q_{inj} is kept at Q_{inj}^{\max} for $\Delta t'$, which can be 3 min, 6 min or 12 min, and then kept at Q_{inj}^{\min} for another $0.5\Delta t'$.

Inj. scheme	Label	Inj. rate, Q_{inj} (m^3/h)	$\Delta T(K) = T_{inj} - T_i$
monotonic	$M1$	360	0/40
	$M2$	288	35/40/ 45
	$M3$	216	40
	$M4$	54	40
Stepwise	$S1$	216 \rightarrow 216 (each 60 h)	40
	$S2$	108 \rightarrow 216 \rightarrow 216 (each 40 h)	40
Cyclic T_{inj}	$C1$	216	40 (Δt) \leftrightarrow 0 ($0.9\Delta t$)
	$C2$	5.4 ($0.5\Delta t'$) \leftrightarrow 54 ($\Delta t'$)	40
Cyclic Q_{inj}	$C3$	28.8 ($0.5\Delta t'$) \leftrightarrow 216 ($\Delta t'$)	40
	$CS1$	(5.4 \leftrightarrow 54) \rightarrow (54 \leftrightarrow 216)	40
Cyclic + stepwise	$CS2$	(5.4 \leftrightarrow 54) \rightarrow (54 \leftrightarrow 108) \rightarrow (108 \leftrightarrow 216)	40

318 The simulation of different stimulation scenarios for a synthetic reservoir with clogged near-borehole zone are
 319 then carried out. First, monotonic injection of cold water with different injection rates, labelled as $M1$ ($Q_{inj} =$
 320 $360 m^3/h$), $M2$ ($Q_{inj} = 288 m^3/h$), $M3$ ($Q_{inj} = 216 m^3/h$) and $M4$ ($Q_{inj} = 54 m^3/h$), are first simulated. Based
 321 on scenario $M1$, the simulations of coupled hydro-mechanical (H-M), thermo-hydraulic (T-H) and fully coupled
 322 THM processes are compared to highlight the influence of the temperature and the initiation and propagation
 323 of fractures. In addition, the effects of different injection temperatures ($\Delta T = 35 K, 40 K, 45 K$) are further
 324 discussed, with simulations based on $M2$.

325 Secondly, two stepwise stimulations, as is shown in Fig. 7a (labelled as $S1$) and Fig. 7b (labelled as $S2$), are
 326 investigated with ΔT fixed at 40 K.

327 Thirdly, different cyclic stimulations, as is shown in Fig. 7c (labelled as $C1$) and Fig. 7d (labelled as $C2$ or
 328 $C3$), are investigated. Scenario $C1$ represents the injection temperature is cycled with fixed injection rate, while
 329 scenarios $C2$ and $C3$ represent the injection rate is cycled with fixed injection temperature. For scenario $C1$,
 330 the ΔT is cycled between 0 K and 40 K, with injection rate fixed at $216 m^3/h$. In one complete cycle, the
 331 ΔT is first kept at 40 K for a period of Δt , which can be 5 hours or 10 hours, and then changed to 0 K for

332 $0.9\Delta t$, which is chosen to avoid numerical divergence (happens if keeping $\Delta T = 0$ K for Δt) while keeping
333 enough time for the reservoir to warm up. In contrast, for scenarios *C2* and *C3*, the maximum injection rate is
334 either $54 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ or $216 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ respectively, while the minimum injection rate is $Q_{\text{inj}}^{\text{max}}/10$ instead of shut in (for
335 numerical convergence and practical reasons, e.g. to avoid the largest seismic events which have been observed
336 during shut-in [43, 44, 4]), with the ΔT fixed at 40 K. In one complete cycle, the injection rate is first kept at
337 its maximum $Q_{\text{inj}}^{\text{max}}$ ($= 216 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ or $54 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$) for a period of $\Delta t'$, which can be 6 min or 12 min, and then the
338 injection rate decreases to $Q_{\text{inj}}^{\text{min}}$ ($= Q_{\text{inj}}^{\text{max}}/10$), which is kept for $\Delta t'/2$. Note that the Δt is much larger than
339 $\Delta t'$ since the heat transfer is much slower than hydraulic process.

340 Fourthly, a combination of cyclic and stepwise stimulation strategy is investigated, as is shown in Fig. 7e
341 (labelled as *CS1*) and Fig. 7f (labelled as *CS2*). Scenario *CS1* is a combination of cyclic injection rate and the
342 stepwise scenario *S1*, while scenarios *CS2* is a combination of cyclic injection rate and the stepwise scenario
343 *S2*. The injection temperature is fixed in both scenarios.

(f) *CS2*

Fig. 7: Visualisation of the investigated scenarios. (a) - (b): Stepwise stimulation scenarios. Injection temperature is fixed at 313 K. (c): The cyclic injection temperature scenario *C1*, where Δt is the cycle period, which is either 5 hours or 10 hours. (d): The cyclic injection rate scenario *C2* or *C3*, where $\Delta t'$ is the cycle period, which is 6 min or 12 min. Maximum injection rate is 54 m³/h or 216 m³/h, while the minimum injection rate is $Q_{inj}^{max}/10$, with injection temperature fixed at 313 K. (e) - (f): Combined cyclic and stepwise stimulation scenarios *CS1* and *CS2*.

344 6. Results and discussion

345 6.1. Reservoir with near-borehole clogging: monotonic stimulation (M1 - M3)

346 This section considers the response of the reservoir with near-borehole clogging to constant injection with
 347 different rates and temperatures. To compare results, an average damage variable (\bar{D}) is defined as the average
 348 value of damage variables over the interface elements along a line through the 5 m radius clogged zone in the
 349 direction of the maximum initial stress σ_H , i.e. the location where the main fracture is expected to be induced
 350 and propagate. \bar{D} can be used to indicate the length of the main fracture and therefore indicate if the main
 351 fracture breaks through the clogged zone. An average damage variable (\bar{D}) of 1 along this line indicates the
 352 main fracture breaks through the 5 m clogged area, thus connecting the wellbore and the un-clogged zone.

353 Fig. 8 compares the pressure response under fixed $Q_{inj} = 360 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ with consideration of coupled THM (with
 354 $\Delta T = 40 \text{ K}$), T-H (with $\Delta T = 40 \text{ K}$) and H-M (with $\Delta T = 0 \text{ K}$) processes in the simulations. Results show that
 355 the injection pressure reaches a constant value at 32.5 MPa quickly for the case of H-M simulation, indicating
 356 that steady state is reached quickly due to the fast pressure diffusion. In contrast, for the case of T-H simulation,
 357 the injection pressure keeps increasing to 39.5 MPa, at which the pressure remains approximately constant, as
 358 a result of the propagation of the cooling front, which increases the viscosity therefore flow resistance. If the
 359 fully coupled THM processes are considered, the injection pressure increases to 34.1 MPa, and then sharply and
 360 continuously decreases as a result of the initiation and propagation of near-borehole fractures. At approximately
 361 $t = 65 \text{ h}$, there is a sudden and significant drop in the pressure, indicating that fracture(s) breaks through the
 362 clogged zone, and connects the wellbore and the un-clogged zone. The comparison highlights the importance of
 363 the consideration of the fully coupled THM processes and the initiation and propagation of fractures.

Fig. 8: Comparison of injection response under coupled THM, T-H, H-M simulations with Q_{inj} fixed at $360 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ (M1 scenario).

364 As shown in Fig. 9, in the M1 scenario (the fully coupled THM case), there is a main fracture propagating
 365 in the direction of the major principal stress and two symmetric fracture branches induced which are oriented
 366 around 45° and -45° (0° is defined to be in the North). To explain this phenomenon, Fig. 9 presents the
 367 fractures evolution with the distribution of the major principal stress σ_1 in the near-borehole zone, taking the
 368 case of $Q_{inj} = 360 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ and $\Delta T = 40 \text{ K}$ as an example. In the first few hours, as is shown in Fig. 9a - 9c,
 369 small fractures are induced around the borehole due to the thermally-induced stress and hydraulic pressure. Although
 370 pore pressure and temperature changes act as isotropic scalar loads, the initial stresses and applied stresses lead

371 to the strongest tensile stress to be in the direction of σ_H (i.e. y direction). Therefore, the main fracture opens
372 first, pushing the side fractures to close. On the other hand, the stress concentration at the borehole wall due
373 to both cold fluid injection causes further tensile stresses which remain lowest in the direction of σ_H and highest
374 at the tip of the already opened fracture. In addition, the mesh also plays a role. The edges of the elements
375 are radially intersecting the borehole in the direction of 45° , 90° and 135° , as shown in Fig. 5b, in which the
376 mesh is presented. In contrast, in other directions, the edges of the elements intersect with the borehole with
377 an angle deviated from the radial direction. Therefore, the normal stress applied on these interface elements
378 (edges) is lower than the major principal stress, and are unable to open the interface elements. Consequently,
379 fracture branches find its easiest way to propagate in the direction of 45° and 135° , while fracture branches
380 in other directions are closed. In comparison, Fig.10 demonstrates the major principal stress distribution at
381 different time steps under only H-M coupled. It shows that the stress is not changing, since hydraulic processes
382 reach steady state in a short time. In addition, the major principal stress remains in compression without
383 contribution from thermally-induced stress, and therefore no fracture happens. This highlights the importance
384 of taking into account the thermal processes in geothermal reservoirs.

Fig. 9: Distribution of the major principal stress σ_1 at different time steps with deformed mesh under $Q_{inj} = 360 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ and $\Delta T = 40 \text{ K}$ ($M1$ scenario). The legend range is -20 MPa (compressive) to 8 MPa (tensile). The deformation is 50 times enlarged, and only the domain within a radius of 10 m is shown.

Fig. 10: Distribution of the major principal stress σ_1 at different time steps with deformed mesh under $Q_{inj} = 360 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ and $\Delta T = 40 \text{ K}$ but with only hydro-mechanical (H-M) coupling. The legend range is -18 MPa (compressive) to -7 MPa (compressive). The deformation is 50 times enlarged, and only the domain within a radius of 10 m is shown.

385 Fig. 11a compares the injection pressure and evolution of the averaged damage variable \bar{D} for scenarios $M1$ to
386 $M4$ with fully coupled THM processes under different injection rate Q_{inj} at fixed $\Delta T = 40 \text{ K}$. As is shown in

387 Fig. 11a, all simulations show substantial damage, with \bar{D} reaching values well above 0.8 when the injection
 388 rate is $216\text{m}^3/\text{h}$, $288\text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, and $360\text{ m}^3/\text{h}$. The sudden drop in injection pressure at approximately $t = 118\text{h}$
 389 and $t = 70\text{h}$ is observed for the cases of Q_{inj} is $288\text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ and $360\text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ respectively, with the corresponding \bar{D}
 390 at 1, indicates a fracture fully penetrating the clogged area. If the injection rate is largely reduced to $54\text{ m}^3/\text{h}$,
 391 the length of the fracture(s) is limited (as is shown in Fig. 12a), although damage is seen to continuously occur.
 392 In addition, the pressure around the tip of the main fracture is built up when the $Q_{\text{inj}} = 216\text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ (Fig. 12b)
 393 but relaxed in the clogged area when $Q_{\text{inj}} = 288\text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ as a result of breaking through the damage area, as is
 394 shown in Fig. 12c, while for the case of $Q_{\text{inj}} = 360\text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, the injection pressure is recovering (Fig.12d) as the
 395 cold front moves further, though the main fracture breakthroughs the clogged area. For the other two cases (Q
 396 $= 54\text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ and $216\text{ m}^3/\text{h}$), no pressure relaxation happens since fracture is shorter and does not breakthrough
 397 the clogged area. A high peak of injection pressure at $28.9\text{ MPa} - 34.1\text{ MPa}$ is observed when Q_{inj} is equal to
 398 or higher than $216\text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, which is significantly higher than the injection pressure (21.5 MPa) for the unclogged
 399 reservoir, and could potentially increase the risk of seismicity as a result of the transient pressure pulse and
 400 equipment failure.

401 Fig. 11b compares stimulation performance with different injection temperatures with the same injection rate
 402 ($M2$ scenario). The results show no significant difference in peak pressure, all at around 31.5 MPa , while a
 403 larger temperature difference of $\Delta T = 45\text{ K}$ and 40 K can result in earlier breakthrough of the clogged zone
 404 and lower injection pressure after reaching the peak pressure. This is because, as shown in Fig. 13c, the
 405 large thermally-induced stress leads to a more damage around the borehole, even complete separation of some
 406 continuum elements, which results in the early stop of simulations due to lack of convergence (for the case
 407 of $\Delta T = 45\text{ K}$), as shown in Fig. 11b. In contrast, $\Delta T = 35\text{ K}$ does not results in a breakthrough of the
 408 clogged zone, with the injection pressure reducing by the least, reducing only to 26 MPa at $t = 120\text{ h}$, with
 409 pressure accumulation around the main fracture, shown in Fig. 13a. In addition, $\Delta T = 40\text{ K}$ is able to create a
 410 breakthrough of the clogged zone, but showing less fracture branching around the borehole (Fig. 13b), compared
 411 to the case when $\Delta T = 45\text{ K}$.

412 Comparing Fig. 11a and 11b, it demonstrates that both increasing the injection rate Q_{inj} and the temperature
 413 difference ΔT can improve the stimulation performance. Yet, increasing the injection rate comes with increasing
 414 peak pressure, which could lead to higher risk of inducing seismicity. In contrast, increasing the temperature
 415 difference seems to be a more safe and efficient method to improve the simulation performance, with the same
 416 peak pressure but significantly more damage and lower injection pressure. However, increasing the temperature
 417 difference should be always implemented with care to meet environment regulations and avoid temperature-
 418 sensitive clogging processes.

Fig. 11: Injection pressure and averaged damage variable evolution under (a) $M1$ to $M4$ scenarios, different injection rate with fixed $\Delta T = 40 \text{ K}$; and (b) $M2$ scenario different ΔT with fixed $Q_{inj} = 288 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$. The damage variable is averaged over the interface elements along a line through the 5 m clogged area from the borehole to the outer radius in the direction of the maximum initial stress σ_H .

Fig. 12: Pressure distribution at $t = 120 \text{ h}$ with deformed mesh under different injection rate (ΔT is fixed at 40 K) - $M1$ to $M4$ scenarios. (a) $Q_{inj} = 54 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$; (b) $Q_{inj} = 216 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$; (c) $Q_{inj} = 288 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$; (d) $Q_{inj} = 360 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$. The deformation is 50 times enlarged, and only the domain within a radius of 10 m is shown.

Fig. 13: Pressure distribution at $t = 120$ h with deformed mesh under different temperature difference (Q_{inj} is fixed at $288 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$) - $M2$ scenario. (a) $\Delta T = 35$ K; (b) $\Delta T = 40$ K; (c) $\Delta T = 45$ K. The deformation is 50 times enlarged, and only the domain within a radius of 10 m is shown.

6.2. Reservoir with near-borehole clogging: stepwise stimulation ($S1 - S2$)

In this section, the stepwise and cyclic stimulation strategies are evaluated, assuming the maximum injection rate $Q_{\text{inj}}^{\text{max}}$ is $216 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ and the maximum temperature difference ΔT^{max} is 40 K.

Fig. 14 compares the injection pressure (p_{inj}) and averaged damage variable (\bar{D}) under monotonic stimulation scenario $M3$ and stepwise stimulation scenario $S1$ and $S2$. It is shown that with stepwise stimulation, compared with monotonic stimulation, a lower maximum injection pressure is achieved with more gradual damage. The three-step scheme ($S2$) leads to better stimulation performance (i.e. a lower maximum injection pressure) than the two-step scheme ($S1$). The highest pressure under monotonic stimulation, shown in Fig. 14a, is about 28.9 MPa, while that under stepwise stimulation $S1$ is about 27.4 MPa and that under $S2$ is 25.4 MPa, shown in Fig. 14a. The decreasing maximum injection pressure is because damage is accumulated in the previous steps, in which the injection rate is low.

In the stepwise simulations, the main fracture is shown to be shorter than that under monotonic stimulation, though the main fracture grows to a slightly smaller length in the end of the stimulation (see Fig. 14b). At the final time step, the main fracture under scenario $S2$ is longer than that under scenario $S1$, leading to a lower pressure at the borehole and around the main fracture, as shown in Fig. 15. In all scenarios, no high-way connection is made between the borehole and the un-clogged zone, thus relatively high pressure remains around the main fracture - which could be addressed by further increasing the injection rate. Fig. 16a - 16d shows the distribution of the major principal stress evolving with time under the scenario. as an example, $S2$. It shows that the tensile region is controlled by the cooling front propagation. When the injection rate is at $54 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, the length of the main fracture remains small, as shown in Fig. 16a and 16b. With the stepwise increase in the injection rate to $108 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ and $216 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, the fracture keeps growing as shown in Fig. 16c and 16d.

440 It can be concluded that the stepwise stimulation strategy has better stimulation performance than mono-
 441 tonic stimulation, as it reduces the required peak injection pressure (substantially), reduces long-term injection
 442 pressures (slightly) and slightly decreases overall reservoir damage.

Fig. 14: Comparison of the (a) injection pressure (p_{inj}); and (b) averaged damage variable (\bar{D}) evolution under monotonic stimulation scenario $M3$ and stepwise stimulation scenarios $S1$ and $S2$. The temperature difference ΔT is fixed at 40 K.

Fig. 15: Pressure distribution of (a) scenario $S1$ and (b) Scenario $S2$ with deformed mesh at $t = 120$ h (deformation enlarged 100 times), and only the domain within a radius of 10 m is shown.

Fig. 16: Distribution of the major principal stress σ_1 at different time steps with deformed mesh under scenario S_2 . (a) $t = 10$ h; (b) $t = 40$ h; (c) $t = 80$ h; (d) $t = 120$ h. The deformation is 50 times enlarged, and only the domain within a radius of 10 m is shown.

443 6.3. Reservoir with near-borehole clogging: cyclic stimulation (C1 - C3))

444 6.3.1. Scenario C1: Cyclic injection temperature

445 Fig. 17a compares the injection pressure response under constant and cyclic-temperature injection. It can be
 446 seen that the highest injection pressure during cyclic-temperature injection is slightly higher than that under
 447 monotonic stimulation. In addition, the main fracture does not breakthrough the clogged zone in either scenario,
 448 as is indicated in Fig. 17b. In Fig. 18, the main fracture and the fracture branching are longer and larger
 449 under monotonic stimulation (the results of pressure are shown in Fig. 12b, which highlight the fracture extend
 450 better) than those under cyclic-temperature stimulation. Yet, there are more secondary fractures induced during
 451 cyclic-temperature stimulation. For monotonic stimulation, 6 visible fracture branches can be seen around the
 452 borehole/main fracture (Fig. 18a), while for cyclic temperature stimulation, 14 fracture branches are induced
 453 (Fig. 18b and 18c). However, the resulting long-term injection pressure is similar in all cases. The extent of
 454 the secondary fractures are seen to be controlled by the time period of the injection of cold water, as is shown
 455 in Fig. 18. To validate the occurrence of more local damages during field monotonic and cyclic temperature
 456 stimulation, micro-seismic monitoring technology, such as distributed acoustic sensing, can be used to monitor
 457 and locate the local damages.

458 It is therefore concluded that cyclic-temperature stimulation (within the bounds of the scenarios considered
 459 here) is generally neither better or worse than monotonic stimulation, but has slightly different characteristics.
 460 Constant injection creates a larger single fracture which breaks through the clogged zone, whereas thermal
 461 cycles create more local damage controlled by the period of the cyclic injection.

Fig. 17: (a) Injection pressure evolution; and (b) corresponding averaged damage variable evolution under monotonic and cyclic-temperature stimulation with $Q_{inj} = 216 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ - scenario C1. Cyclic period is 5 hours and 10 hours.

Fig. 18: Temperature distribution at $t = 120 \text{ h}$ with deformed mesh under (a) monotonic ($Q_{inj}^{max} = 216 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$), (b) 5-hour and (c) 10-hour cyclic-temperature stimulation ($\Delta T = 40 \text{ K} \leftrightarrow 0 \text{ K}$) - scenario C1. The deformation is 100 times enlarged.

462 6.3.2. Scenario C2 & C3: Cyclic injection rate

463 In Scenario C2, cyclic stimulation with a lower maximum injection rate ($54 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$) is investigated. Fig. 19a
 464 compares the pressure response and averaged damage variable under monotonic stimulation M4 and 12 min
 465 cyclic stimulation with and without the fatigue damage. It shows that the peak pressure under monotonic
 466 stimulation is slightly higher than cyclic stimulation. This is because the cyclic injection scheme slows down the
 467 pressure build up and at the same time, near-borehole damage is accumulated, resulting lower peak pressure. In

468 the 5-day stimulation, the monotonic scheme shows the best stimulation performance, with a lower maximum
 469 injection pressure and longer main fracture (indicated by the averaged damage variable) after the first 20 hours.
 470 In addition, a comparison of the injection pressure under cyclic stimulation with and without fatigue damage
 471 included, demonstrates that fatigue damage makes a minor difference, only causing slightly earlier fracture
 472 growth, as can be seen in the enlarged part in Fig. 19a and the damage evolution in Fig. 19b.
 473 Moreover, factors that could impact the fatigue effect are also investigated. Fig. 20a compares the injection
 474 pressure under different frequency (6 min and 12 min)
 475 Result shows that even if the cyclic frequency is increased, the fatigue effect makes little difference. The reason
 476 is likely that the growing fractures make the pressure difficult to maintain at a level that can induce fatigue
 477 damage within a reasonable number of cycles. This can be seen in Fig. 21a and 21c, in which the major
 478 principal stress σ_1 at the fracture tip is shown to be around 3 MPa at $t = 120$ h, smaller than the tensile
 479 strength (4.8 MPa) due to stress relaxation after fracture growth, indicated by the increased averaged damage
 480 variable at $t = 120$ h shown in Fig. 19a. The continuous increase in the averaged damage variable demonstrates
 481 the continuous fracture growth, therefore continuous stress relaxation. In contrast, during the period when the
 482 averaged damage variable keeps the constant (i.e. no fracture growth), the fatigue effect still does not make
 483 significant difference. This is because the stress applied on the interface element at the fracture tip is too small
 484 to induce effective fatigue damage within the cycles before fracture growing. This can be seen for the case of
 485 cyclic stimulation without damage variable, shown in Fig. 21b, the σ_1 at the fracture tip is around 4 MPa,
 486 leading to the ratio σ_A/σ_{n0} (i.e. $4/4.8$) equal to 83%, which leads to a fatigue life of around 30 000 cycles
 487 (see Fig. 6). Consequently, significant fatigue damage cannot be achieved with the current cyclic scheme. In
 488 addition, the fitted S-N curve can also make a difference. The parameter a is perturbed to evaluate the impact
 489 of the S-N curve. As is shown in Fig. 6, one S-N curve is fitted based on all the collected experimental data,
 490 leading to the $a = -0.0361$, while another S-N curve is taken such that $a = -0.0542$ and the fitted curve almost
 491 is the lowest envelop of the scattered experimental data. Fig. 20b shows the injection pressure response under
 492 different assumptions of the S-N curve. A higher slope leads to faster failure, i.e. less cycles. And the result
 493 shows this trend in Fig. 20b, in which the injection pressure reduces earlier in the case of $a = -0.0542$ than
 494 that in the case of $a = -0.0361$.

Fig. 19: (a) Injection pressure response and (b) averaged damage variable evolution for scenario C2 under 12-min cyclic stimulation ($Q_{inj} = 54 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$) with and without fatigue damage variable included in the traction-separation law.

Fig. 20: Comparison of injection pressure response for scenario C2 under (a) different frequency (6 min and 12 min); (b) different S-N curve ($a = -0.0361$ or -0.0180).

Fig. 21: Horizontal stress (σ_x) distribution at $t = 120$ h with deformed mesh under (a) monotonic stimulation (scenario $M4$); (b) cyclic stimulation without fatigue damage (scenario $C2$); (c) cyclic stimulation with fatigue damage (scenario $C2$). The deformation is 100 times enlarged, and only the domain within a radius of 10 m is shown.

495 In scenario $C3$, cyclic stimulation with higher maximum injection rate ($216 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$) is investigated. Fig. 22
 496 compares the pressure response and averaged damage variable under monotonic stimulation $M3$ and cyclic
 497 stimulation $C3$ with and without fatigue damage variable included. It shows the injection pressure under cyclic
 498 stimulation is always slightly higher than the monotonic stimulation, except for the initial stage where the cyclic
 499 stimulation outperforms the monotonic stimulation, as also observed in scenario $C2$. This is because the higher
 500 injection rate leads to quick fracture growth, while cyclic reduction in injection rate slows down the fracture
 501 growth. In addition, the underlying mechanism why the fatigue damage does not make a difference is the same
 502 with that explained earlier, therefore not repeated here.

Fig. 22: Injection pressure response and averaged damage variable evolution under 12-min cyclic stimulation ($Q_{inj} = 216 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$) with and without fatigue damage variable included in the traction-separation law - scenario *C3*.

503 *6.4. Reservoir with near-borehole clogging: combined cyclic and stepwise stimulation (CS1 - CS2)*

504 In scenarios *CS1* and *CS2*, the combined cyclic and stepwise stimulation strategy is investigated. Fig. 23a
 505 compares the pressure response under monotonic stimulation and stimulation scenarios *CS1* and *CS2*. It shows
 506 that the highest spike under monotonic stimulation (28.9 MPa) is significantly reduced to 28 MPa and 25.8
 507 MPa by changing the stimulation scenario to *CS1* and *CS2* respectively. Yet, the highest spike is higher than
 508 that under only stepwise stimulations, especially the three-step stimulation *S2*. This is because the continuous
 509 injection in each step causes longer fracture (as can be seen in Fig. 23b) at the end of each step. When
 510 the injection rate is increased, the longer fracture leads to lower peak pressure than that under *CS1* and *CS2*
 511 scenarios. In addition, at $t = 80 \text{ h} - 120 \text{ h}$, the injection pressure under *S1* and *S2* is significantly lower than that
 512 under *CS1* and *CS2* respectively. It therefore can be concluded that stepwise combined with cyclic stimulation
 513 is better than monotonic stimulation, but is inferior than only stepwise stimulation.

Fig. 23: (a) Injection pressure response under combined cyclic and stepwise stimulation (Scenario $CS1$ and $CS2$); and (b) Corresponding averaged damage variable \bar{D} .

514 In terms of the total energy input, Fig. 24 compares the total mechanical (pumping) energy input under different
 515 stimulation scenarios. The energy is quantified by considering the pumping energy only, assuming that changes
 516 in temperature can be achieved by using extracted water mixed with water at ambient temperature (as the
 517 temperatures used neither exceed extracted temperatures nor are lower than ambient). The mechanical losses
 518 in the wells are ignored, since the wells are designed for higher flow rate than used in the stimulation, thus
 519 losses are small.

520 It show that cyclic injection temperature stimulation leads to the highest total energy input after 120-hour
 521 operation, followed by monotonic stimulation scenario $C3$, with a 0.08 TJ difference. This is attributed to the
 522 increases in viscosity when decreasing the temperature which result in a higher required injection pressure (see
 523 Fig. 23). The cyclic injection rate protocol has further reductions in energy input, with the stepwise or stepwise
 524 combined with cyclic injection rate protocols leading to the least total energy input due to its lower injection
 525 rate in the first steps and its alternated injection rate, using around half of the input energy than monotonic
 526 injection, leading to a significant cost saving. In context of produced energy (albeit energy production is thermal
 527 energy and input energy is likely to be electrical), the amounts used are negligible, with such a system producing
 528 in the magnitude of TJs per day (depending on the injection temperature).

Fig. 24: Total energy input under different stimulation scenarios, including monotonic stimulation ($M3$), Stepwise stimulation $S1$ and $S2$, cyclic injection temperature stimulation $C1$ (with $\Delta t = 10$ hours or 5 hours), cyclic injection rate stimulation $C3$, as well as stepwise combined with cyclic injection rate stimulation $CS1$ and $CS2$.

529 7. Conclusion

530 Thermo-hydro-mechanical (THM) finite element simulations of cold water injection into a reservoir are per-
 531 formed to evaluate the potential for thermo-hydraulic stimulation of clogged reservoirs. Interface elements are
 532 inserted between all continuum elements to allow for fracture initiation and propagation. The simulations as-
 533 sume a 2D plane strain condition, therefore do not include 3D effects, such as out-of-plane fracture branching,
 534 stress arching, or thermal convection, which could influence details of the fracture propagation patterns and
 535 pressure response. In addition, the heat exchange between the wellbore fluid, casing and the formation is not
 536 included in this model, and could overestimate the thermally-induced stresses. Yet, considering the relatively
 537 high flow rate, which leads to higher heat convection, the overestimation is limited.

538 For a clogged reservoir, simulations of various stimulation strategies - constant, stepwise, cyclic, and combined
 539 stepwise-cyclic injection - reveal that stepwise stimulation consistently provides the most favourable outcomes.
 540 It achieves the lowest peak injection pressure (4.4 MPa above the initial reservoir pressure, compared to 7.9 MPa
 541 in the monotonic case for $Q_{inj} = 216 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ and $\Delta T = 40 \text{ K}$) and maintains slightly lower long-term injection
 542 pressures. In addition, it uses the least input energy to achieve this. Cyclic-temperature stimulation (within the
 543 bounds of the scenarios considered here) yields broadly comparable results to monotonic stimulation but with
 544 distinct fracture patterns: constant injection promotes the formation of a single dominant fracture through the
 545 clogged zone, whereas thermal cycles induce more distributed damage controlled by the thermal cycle period.
 546 However, due to the lower viscosity of injected cooler water uses the most input energy. Cyclic-injection-rate
 547 stimulation exhibits marginal improvement or degradation relative to monotonic stimulation, depending on
 548 the injection rate, with fatigue effects remaining negligible. A combined stepwise-cyclic strategy may enhance
 549 stimulation performance compared to monotonic stimulation, and consumes least pumping energy than stepwise

550 stimulation alone under the investigated conditions. Although the enhanced permeability may decrease after
551 stimulation with the stress recovery, continuous reinjection of cold water, as a necessary operation in geothermal
552 projects, can relieve this impact.

553 **Author contributions**

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555 Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualisation.

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557 ing - Review & Editing, Supervision.

558 **Josselin Ouf:** Software, Formal Analysis, Writing - Review & Editing.

559 **Philip J. Vardon:** Conceptualisation, Methodology, Validation, Formal Analysis, Writing - Review & Editing,
560 Supervision, Project Administration, Funding Acquisition.

561 **Declaration of competing interest**

562 The authors have nothing to declare.

563 **Acknowledgement**

564 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
565 under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 956965. Support and help from Joaquín Liaudat
566 throughout this research is gratefully acknowledged.

567 **Appendix A. Method to reduce hydraulic and thermal artificial compliance**

568 The placement of interface elements between continuum elements has been shown not to affect the stress, pres-
569 sure or temperature fields of intact rock when parameters are appropriately chosen. In particular, the stiffness
570 of the interface elements should be set high enough to reduce the mechanical artificial compliance without caus-
571 ing numerical instability. Similarly, to properly address the thermal and hydraulic artificial conductivity, the
572 transversal hydraulic transmissivity should be set as high as possible to minimise the pressure and temperature
573 drops across the interface elements.

574 However, a high transversal hydraulic transmissivity can result in fast heat convection across the interface ele-
575 ments. It is well known that fast heat convection in comparison to conduction can lead to numerical oscillation.
576 The Péclet number, a dimensionless number that quantifies the relative importance of convective heat transport
577 compared to conductive heat transport, is used to characterise the dominant heat transfer mechanism. It is
578 defined as:

$$Pe = \frac{\rho_w c_{pw} h v_w^{b/t}}{2\lambda_w} \quad (\text{transversal}) \quad (\text{A.1})$$

579 where ρ_w [m³/h], c_{pw} [J/kg·K] and λ_w [W/m·K] are the water density, specific heat capacity and heat conduc-
580 tivity respectively. $v_w^{b/t}$ [m/s] is the transversal fluid velocity (from bottom or top side of the interface element).
581 h [m] is the element length.

582 A high Péclet corresponds to a convection-dominated transfer mechanism. In Luo et al. [26], it is shown that
583 high longitudinal heat convection within the interface elements can result in numerical oscillation, and that

584 adding an artificial conductivity can stabilise the solution. In the present case, transversal heat convection
 585 will also be high due to the imposed high transversal transmissivity. Therefore, in this section, an artificial
 586 conductivity is added to the transversal heat transfer terms. It is expressed as:

$$\lambda_a = \delta \rho_w c_{pw} h \left| v_w^{b/t} \right| \quad (\text{transversal}) \quad (\text{A.2})$$

587 where δ is a tuning parameter. Consequently, the Péclet number with stabilisation reads:

$$Pe = \frac{\rho_w c_{pw} h v_w^{b/t}}{2(\lambda_a + \lambda_w)} \quad (\text{transversal}) \quad (\text{A.3})$$

588 To demonstrate the stabilisation technique, thermo-hydraulic (T-H) simulations of the injection of cold water
 589 using the model equipped with interface elements with and without stabilisation are first compared. Then, T-H
 590 simulations using the model with interface elements and the model without interface elements are compared
 591 to demonstrate the capability of the modelling approach (i.e. increasing the transversal hydraulic conductivity
 592 of the interface element with stabilised technique) to reproduce the thermal and hydraulic fields of the intact
 593 rock. The parameters of the continuum and interface elements as well as boundary and initial conditions are
 594 the same as is presented earlier in Tab. 1 and Tab. 2. The injection rate Q_{inj} is assumed to be $72 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ with
 595 injection temperature at 313 K .

596 Fig. A1 compares temperature fields calculated without and with stabilisation technique, of simulations on the
 597 domain including interface elements. Significant oscillation is seen to occur if no stabilisation technique is used,
 598 and the simulation stops at $t = 30 \text{ s}$ due to lack of numerical convergence. In contrast, when the stabilisation
 599 technique is used (with $\delta \times h = 10 \text{ m}$), the simulation is seen to run smoothly and continuously without any
 600 numerical oscillation.

(a) Temperature field without stabilisation. $t = 30$ s

(b) Temperature field with stabilisation ($\delta \times h = 10$). $t = 2000$ s

Fig. A1: Comparison of temperature fields (model region within radius of 10 meters is shown here) with and without stabilisation technique for high Péclet number. The simulation without stabilisation is stopped at $t = 30$ s due to numerical divergence and temperature solution is with numerical oscillation. The black spots indicate values outside the legend range 313 K - 353 K. In contrast, the simulation with stabilisation can run smoothly without oscillation.

601 The second set of simulations investigates whether the model equipped with interface elements, utilising high
 602 transversal transmissivity and stabilisation, can reproduce the hydraulic and thermal fields of intact rock. To
 603 investigate this, two model domains are used and the results compared. The first model only consists of
 604 continuum elements, representing intact rock, while the other is composed of continuum elements and interface
 605 elements. Two variants of the model with interface elements are used to investigate the impact of the transversal
 606 hydraulic transmissivity. As before, thermo-hydraulic simulations with same boundary and initial conditions
 607 are performed. Figs. A2a and A2b compare the spatial distribution of pressure and temperature of all three
 608 results. Fig. A2c presents the temperature results for an additional time step of the intact and most successful
 609 stabilised solution. The results show that when the transversal hydraulic transmissivity of the interface elements
 610 is $1\text{E-}10$ m^2 , the temperature and pressure distributions are imperceptibly different from those of the model
 611 without interface elements. In contrast, when the transversal hydraulic transmissivity is $1\text{E-}12$ m^2 , there is a

612 large difference in the zone with the interface elements. The comparison confirms that the values of transversal
613 fluid/heat transmissivity must be carefully selected, in order to have realistic results, but this may require the
614 use of a stabilisation technique to address the resulting numerical oscillation due to high Péclet number.

(a) Pressure profile at $t = 1440$ h

(b) Temperature profile at $t = 1440$ h

(c) Temperature profile after 5 and 1440 hours of cold water injection

Fig. A2: Comparison of (a) pressure ($t = 1440$ h) and (b) temperature ($t = 1440$ h) distributions with and without interface elements inserted in between all the continuum elements in the region with a radius of 10 meters. When the transversal hydraulic conductivity is $1E-10 \text{ m}^2$ respectively, the pressure and temperature distribution can be reproduced. (c) Comparison of temperature distribution evolving with time, of the model equipped with interface element ($t^{b/t} = 1E-10 \text{ m}^2$) and without interface element.

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